

Original data for publication "Resolving dynamics and function of transient states in single enzyme molecules" by Sanabria et al.

The following files are available on Zenodo under DOI 10.5281/zenodo.3376527:

- * eTCSPC_wildtype.zip contains all eTCSPC FRET data including reference measurements used for derivation of DA distances.
- * Single_molecule_wildtype.zip contains raw single-molecule data used for filtered FCS and MFD analysis: calibration measurements (e.g. for detection efficiency, instrument response function (IRF), background, and g-factor calibration) and measurement data.
- * Single_molecule_functional_variants.zip contains raw single-molecule data for derivation of the kinetic scheme.
- * EPR_wildtype.zip contains EPR data.
- * FRET_screening_of_PDB_structures.zip contains a table of experimental distances and errors for each DA pair (corresponding to Supplementary Table 2), and a file with an overview on the FRET screening of the PDB structures.

Each of the subfolders in eTCSPC_wildtype.zip, Single_molecule_wildtype.zip and Single_molecule_functional_variants.zip for a DA pair X-Y contain a X-Y.yml file describing the setup and referencing all data relevant for the analysis of the measurement.

Filename of meta file on Zenodo	
eTCSPC\5-44\5-44.yml	eTCSPC data for variant E5pAcF/S44C
eTCSPC\5-132\5-132.yml	eTCSPC data for variant E5pAcF/N132C
eTCSPC\8-69\8-69.yml	eTCSPC data for variant R8pAcF/Q69C
eTCSPC\8-86\8-86.yml	eTCSPC data for variant R8pAcF/P86C
eTCSPC\8-119\8-119.yml	eTCSPC data for variant R8pAcF/R119C
eTCSPC\8-132\8-132.yml	eTCSPC data for variant R8pAcF/N132C
eTCSPC\19-69\19-69.yml	eTCSPC data for variant K19pAcF/Q69C
eTCSPC\19-86\19-86.yml	eTCSPC data for variant K19pAcF/P86C
eTCSPC\19-119\19-119.yml	eTCSPC data for variant K19pAcF/R119C
eTCSPC\19-132\19-132.yml	eTCSPC data for variant K19pAcF/N132C
eTCSPC\22-127\22-127.yml	eTCSPC data for variant E22pAcF/D127C
eTCSPC\36-86\36-86.yml	eTCSPC data for variant S36pAcF/P86C
eTCSPC\36-132\36-132.yml	eTCSPC data for variant S36pAcF/N132C
eTCSPC\44-69\44-69.yml	eTCSPC data for variant S44pAcF/Q69C
eTCSPC\44-86\44-86.yml	eTCSPC data for variant S44pAcF/P86C
eTCSPC\44-119\44-119.yml	eTCSPC data for variant S44pAcF/R119C
eTCSPC\44-127\44-127.yml	eTCSPC data for variant S44pAcF/D127C
eTCSPC\44-132\44-132.yml	eTCSPC data for variant S44pAcF/N132C
eTCSPC\44-150\44-150.yml	eTCSPC data for variant S44pAcF/I150C
eTCSPC\55-69\55-69.yml	eTCSPC data for variant N55pAcF/Q69C
eTCSPC\55-119\55-119.yml	eTCSPC data for variant N55pAcF/R119C
eTCSPC\55-132\55-132.yml	eTCSPC data for variant N55pAcF/N132C
eTCSPC\55-150\55-150.yml	eTCSPC data for variant N55pAcF/I150C
eTCSPC\60-86\60-86.yml	eTCSPC data for variant K60pAcF/P86C
eTCSPC\60-119\60-119.yml	eTCSPC data for variant K60pAcF/R119C
eTCSPC\60-132\60-132.yml	eTCSPC data for variant K60pAcF/N132C
eTCSPC\60-150\60-150.yml	eTCSPC data for variant K60pAcF/I150C

eTCSPC\69-86\69-86.yml	eTCSPC data for variant Q69pAcF/P86C
eTCSPC\69-119\69-119.yml	eTCSPC data for variant Q69pAcF/R119C
eTCSPC\69-132\69-132.yml	eTCSPC data for variant Q69pAcF/N132C
eTCSPC\69-150\69-150.yml	eTCSPC data for variant Q69pAcF/I150C
eTCSPC\70-119\70-119.yml	eTCSPC data for variant D70pAcF/R119C
eTCSPC\70-132\70-132.yml	eTCSPC data for variant D70pAcF/N132C
Single_molecule_wildtype\5-44\5-44.yml	Single-molecule data for variant E5pAcF/S44C
Single_molecule_wildtype\5-44\5-44.yml	Single-molecule data for variant E5pAcF/S44C
Single_molecule_wildtype\5-132\5-132.yml	Single-molecule data for variant E5pAcF/N132C
Single_molecule_wildtype\8-69\8-69.yml	Single-molecule data for variant R8pAcF/Q69C
Single_molecule_wildtype\8-86\8-86.yml	Single-molecule data for variant R8pAcF/P86C
Single_molecule_wildtype\8-119\8-119.yml	Single-molecule data for variant R8pAcF/R119C
Single_molecule_wildtype\8-132\8-132.yml	Single-molecule data for variant R8pAcF/N132C
Single_molecule_wildtype\19-69\19-69.yml	Single-molecule data for variant K19pAcF/Q69C
Single_molecule_wildtype\19-86\19-86.yml	Single-molecule data for variant K19pAcF/P86C
Single_molecule_wildtype\19-119\19-119.yml	Single-molecule data for variant K19pAcF/R119C
Single_molecule_wildtype\19-132\19-132.yml	Single-molecule data for variant K19pAcF/N132C
Single_molecule_wildtype\22-127\22-127.yml	Single-molecule data for variant E22pAcF/D127C
Single_molecule_wildtype\36-86\36-86.yml	Single-molecule data for variant S36pAcF/P86C
Single_molecule_wildtype\36-132\36-132.yml	Single-molecule data for variant S36pAcF/N132C
Single_molecule_wildtype\44-69\44-69.yml	Single-molecule data for variant S44pAcF/Q69C
Single_molecule_wildtype\44-86\44-86.yml	Single-molecule data for variant S44pAcF/P86C
Single_molecule_wildtype\44-119\44-119.yml	Single-molecule data for variant S44pAcF/R119C
Single_molecule_wildtype\44-127\44-127.yml	Single-molecule data for variant S44pAcF/D127C
Single_molecule_wildtype\44-132\44-132.yml	Single-molecule data for variant S44pAcF/N132C
Single_molecule_wildtype\44-150\44-150.yml	Single-molecule data for variant S44pAcF/I150C
Single_molecule_wildtype\55-69\55-69.yml	Single-molecule data for variant N55pAcF/Q69C
Single_molecule_wildtype\55-119\55-119.yml	Single-molecule data for variant N55pAcF/R119C
Single_molecule_wildtype\55-132\55-132.yml	Single-molecule data for variant N55pAcF/N132C
Single_molecule_wildtype\55-150\55-150.yml	Single-molecule data for variant N55pAcF/I150C
Single_molecule_wildtype\60-86\60-86.yml	Single-molecule data for variant K60pAcF/P86C
Single_molecule_wildtype\60-119\60-119.yml	Single-molecule data for variant K60pAcF/R119C
Single_molecule_wildtype\60-132\60-132.yml	Single-molecule data for variant K60pAcF/N132C
Single_molecule_wildtype\60-150\60-150.yml	Single-molecule data for variant K60pAcF/I150C
Single_molecule_wildtype\69-86\69-86.yml	Single-molecule data for variant Q69pAcF/P86C
Single_molecule_wildtype\69-119\69-119.yml	Single-molecule data for variant Q69pAcF/R119C
Single_molecule_wildtype\69-132\69-132.yml	Single-molecule data for variant Q69pAcF/N132C
Single_molecule_wildtype\69-150\69-150.yml	Single-molecule data for variant Q69pAcF/I150C
Single_molecule_wildtype\70-119\70-119.yml	Single-molecule data for variant D70pAcF/R119C
Single_molecule_wildtype\70-132\70-132.yml	Single-molecule data for variant D70pAcF/N132C
Single_molecule_functional_variants\44-150\44-150.yml	Single-molecule data for function variant S44pAcF/I150C
Single_molecule_functional_variants\44-150+pep\44-150+pep.yml	Single-molecule data for function variant S44pAcF/I150C with peptidoglycan
Single_molecule_functional_variants\44-150-E11A\44-150-E11A.yml	Single-molecule data for function variant S44pAcF/I150C/E11A
Single_molecule_functional_variants\44-150-E11A+pep\44-150-E11A+pep.yml	Single-molecule data for function variant S44pAcF/I150C/E11A with peptidoglycan

Single_molecule_functional_variants\44-150-R137E\44-150-R137E.yml	Single-molecule data for function variant S44pACf/1150C/R137E
Single_molecule_functional_variants\44-150-T26E\44-150-T26E.yml	Single-molecule data for function variant S44pACf/1150C/T26E
Single_molecule_functional_variants\44-150-T26E+pep\44-150-T26E+pep.yml	Single-molecule data for function variant S44pACf/1150C/T26E with peptidoglycan

The subfolders for eTCSPC measurements for DA pair X-Y contain the following files:

Filename	Purpose
X-Y_DA.dat	Data for measurement
X-Y_D0.dat	Data for donor-only reference measurement
IRF_D0.dat	Instrument response function for donor-only reference measurement
IRF_DA.dat	Instrument response function for FRET measurement

The subfolders for a single-molecule measurement for DA pair X-Y contain the following subfolders

Folder name ¹	Content
"X-Y smd 0M" or "X Y DA sm" or "X_Y_0muera_sm" or "T4L_X_Y_FRET" or "T4L-X-Y-DA-smd" or "X_Y_da_sm"	Measurement data
"IRF" or "irf" or "H2O" or "water" or "h2o"	Instrument response function (IRF)
"DNA" or "dna"	Calibration measurement for detection efficiency
"pbs0M" or "pbs" or "buffer" or "buffer_HS" or "PBS" or "buffer_tween20" or "buff_0m" or "Buffer 00M"	Calibration measurement for background
"Rh101" and "Rh110" or "Rhod101" and "Rhod110" or "Rhod110thick" or "rho101" and "rho110"	Measurements for g-factor calibration

¹ Folder names might vary between subfolders